

1 **2026 Swiss society of Infectious diseases recommendations for**
2 ***Clostridioides difficile* Infection (CDI)**

3 Benoit Guery¹, Werner C. Albrich², Silvio D Brugger³, Romain Martischang⁴, Virginie Prendki^{4,5},
4 Giacomo Stroffolini¹, Sarah Tschudin-Sutter⁶.

5
6 ¹Infectious Diseases Service, Lausanne University Hospital and University of Lausanne,
7 Lausanne, Switzerland

8 ²Division of Infectious Diseases, Infection Prevention and Travel Medicine, HOCH Health
9 Ostschweiz, St Gallen Cantonal Hospital, St Gallen, Switzerland

10 ³Department of Infectious Diseases and Hospital Epidemiology, University Hospital Zurich,
11 University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

12 ⁴Division of Infectious Diseases, Geneva University Hospitals, Geneva, Switzerland

13 ⁵Department of internal medicine, rehabilitation and geriatrics, Geneva University Hospitals,
14 Geneva, Switzerland

15 ⁶Division of Infectious Diseases, University Hospital Basel, Basel, Switzerland and Department
16 of Clinical Research, University Hospital Basel, and University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

17
18 **Correspondance:** Pr Benoit Guery, Infectious Diseases Service, Lausanne University Hospital,
19 BH10-553, Rue du Bugnon 46, 1011 Lausanne, Switzerland. Email: benoit.guery@chuv.ch

22 **Abstract:** The most recent Swiss Society for Infectious diseases recommendations for
23 *Clostridioides difficile* infection (CDI) in Switzerland were based on the 2018 American
24 guidelines. Since then, a large number of new studies have been published, and updated
25 international guidelines—both European and American—have introduced substantial
26 innovations in CDI diagnosis and treatment.
27 This document represents a consensus statement developed by an SSI-appointed group of
28 experts. The objective of these national guidelines is to provide a comprehensive, evidence-
29 based, and context-specific framework for the diagnosis, treatment, prevention, and follow-
30 up of CDI across all stages of disease. By synthesizing the latest clinical evidence, recent
31 international guideline updates, and national organizational and regulatory considerations,
32 these guidelines aim to harmonize clinical practice, promote high-quality and equitable
33 patient care, and support clinicians in making informed, patient-centered decisions within the
34 Swiss healthcare system. These guidelines are endorsed by the Swiss Society for Infectious
35 diseases.
36

37 Introduction

38 *Clostridioides difficile* infection (CDI) is a major cause of healthcare-associated morbidity and
39 mortality and represents a persistent and evolving challenge for national healthcare systems
40 [1,2]. The incidence and severity of CDI disproportionately affect older adults, patients with
41 multiple comorbidities, and individuals exposed to antibiotics or healthcare environments, with
42 recurrence occurring in up to one third of cases and contributing substantially to patient burden
43 and healthcare costs [3]. Over recent years, important advances have been made in the
44 understanding of CDI epidemiology, pathophysiology, diagnostics, and treatment, prompting
45 significant updates to international recommendations [4–7]. These include refined diagnostic
46 algorithms prioritizing detection of free toxins, a shift away from metronidazole as routine
47 therapy, expanded use of fidaxomicin and optimized vancomycin regimens, and the increasing
48 role of fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) therapies for recurrent disease. FMT has become
49 an established, highly effective intervention, raising regulatory and implementation
50 considerations that vary across countries [4,8]. New live biotherapeutic products have
51 emerged, and will probably challenge FMT in the future. Despite these advances, heterogeneity
52 in clinical practice persists, particularly with respect to severity assessment, prevention of
53 recurrence, management of severe and complicated CDI, and integration of novel therapies
54 within national regulatory frameworks. The objective of these national guidelines is to provide
55 an updated comprehensive, evidence-based, and context-specific framework for the diagnosis,
56 treatment, prevention, and follow-up of CDI across all stages of disease. Previous SSI guidelines
57 were based on 2018 international literature which is by now largely outdated. By summarizing
58 the most recent clinical evidence, international guideline updates, and national organizational
59 and regulatory considerations, this document aims to harmonize clinical practice, support high-
60 quality and equitable patient care, and guide clinicians in making informed, patient-centered
61 decisions in the management of CDI.

62

63 Method

64 A panel of physicians from different medical specialties (infectious diseases, geriatrics, infection
65 control) and different Swiss tertiary care hospitals was constituted. The members of this panel
66 were selected by the Swiss Infectious Diseases Society committee according to their expertise
67 in the topic. The work was distributed in four working groups (WG): definitions (WG1), risk
68 factors (WG2), treatment (WG3), and prevention and infection control (WG4).
69 Practical questions to answer were defined for each WG. During a first step, each WG worked
70 independently on literature review, data analyses and elaboration of proposed recommenda-
71 tions. Results of analyses and recommendations were presented during a virtual session
72 attended by all participants. These recommendations were discussed during the session and
73 the draft amended and validated afterwards. In case of substantial disagreement, the issues
74 were referred to each WG for reassessment and elaboration of a revised proposition, which
75 was again submitted to the appreciation of the whole panel. The final recommendations were
76 consensus-based and needed the approval of all the panel. Final recommendations were
77 validated by the SSI guidelines board. The detailed workflow of the guideline development and
78 the listing of participants of the different WGs are provided in Tables S1 and S2, respectively.
79 This analysis formed the basis for adapting and contextualizing international evidence-based
80 recommendations to the Swiss healthcare setting.

81

82 Definitions

83 Definitions were adapted from the most recent European and American guidelines [4,5,7] and
84 summarized in **Figure 1**.

- 85 • **Clinical symptoms compatible with CDI** [9]
 - 86 ○ **Diarrhea** is defined as ≥ 3 loose stools, i.e. Bristol stool scale 6-7, in 24 hours
 - 87 ○ **Ileus**: Digestive dysfunction with vomiting or nausea with intolerance of oral
 - 88 intake and absence of stool, plus radiological signs of intestinal distension
 - 89 ○ **Toxic Megacolon**: colonic distension greater than 6 cm with signs of sepsis [10].
 - 90 Distension is typically measured at the transverse colon on radiographic
 - 91 imaging, but US guidelines prioritize a comprehensive clinical and radiographic
 - 92 assessment over strict reliance on this measurement alone [6]. The cut-offs for
 - 93 rectal and caecal measurement are respectively $> 4\text{-}5$ cm and > 9 cm.
- 94 • **An episode of CDI** is defined as the association of 3 parameters:
 - 95 ○ Clinical features including
 - 96 ■ Clinical symptoms compatible with CDI
 - 97 ■ Pseudomembranous colitis diagnosed after endoscopy, colectomy, or
 - 98 autopsy
 - 99 ○ Microbiological evidence of *C. difficile* (at best evidence of free toxins): cf
 - 100 microbiological methods.
 - 101 ○ No alternate diagnosis
- 102 • **Microbiological methods**
 - 103 ○ Stool processing
 - 104 ■ The Infectious Diseases Society of America and the American Society for
 - 105 Microbiology state that proper storage is critical to prevent toxin
 - 106 degradation, which can lead to false negative results in toxin-based
 - 107 assays [11].
 - 108 ■ Experimental data demonstrate that storage at 4°C preserves *C. difficile*
 - 109 cytotoxin activity for several days, while storage at -20°C leads to
 - 110 significant loss of toxin activity, especially with repeated freeze-thaw
 - 111 cycles, and that -80°C is preferable for long-term storage to maintain
 - 112 toxin integrity [12]. Additional studies confirm that freezing at -20°C can
 - 113 detrimentally affect toxin stability, particularly in diluted specimens,
 - 114 whereas -80°C preserves toxin detection by immunoassay [13].
 - 115 ■ In the clinical routine, stool samples for *C. difficile* toxin testing should
 - 116 be refrigerated at 4°C if processed within 72 hours, or frozen at -80°C for
 - 117 longer storage, and that -20°C is not recommended due to the risk of
 - 118 toxin degradation and false negative results.
 - 119 ■ Rectal swabs may be tested with NAAT for patients with ileus (inform the
 - 120 laboratory)
 - 121 ○ The recommended diagnostic approach is a multistep algorithm: initial
 - 122 screening with a sensitive glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH) antigen assay,
 - 123 followed by confirmatory testing for toxins A and B using enzyme immunoassay
 - 124 (EIA) or immunochromatographic methods. Nucleic acid amplification tests
 - 125 (NAATs) may be used as part of the algorithm or alone in symptomatic patients,
 - 126 but NAATs alone may detect colonization rather than active infection, so
 - 127 combining NAAT with toxin testing improves specificity for CDI [14]. Toxigenic
 - 128 culture and cell cytotoxin assays are considered gold standards but are rarely
 - 129 used due to labor intensity and slow turnaround time.

- 130 ○ In 2021, the European guidelines suggested an alternative approach
131 emphasizing the importance of free toxin detection [4] :
- 132 ▪ Free toxins measured by enzyme immunoassay
133 OR
134 ▪ Positive nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT) preferably with a low cycle
135 threshold (Ct) value. Based on the literature, several thresholds were
136 proposed between 26 and 27 [15,16].
- 137 ● **Severe forms** are defined by one of the following criteria:
 - 138 ○ Leukocytosis with a white blood cell count of $\geq 15\,000$ cells/mL [4,5]
 - 139 ○ Serum creatinine level >1.5 mg/dL ($>132\mu\text{mol/L}$) [5] or rise in serum creatinine
140 $>50\%$ of baseline [4,5]
 - 141 ○ Core body temperature $>38.5^\circ\text{C}$ [4]
 - 142 ● **Severe complicated forms** are defined by the presence of one of the following
143 attributed to CDI:
 - 144 ○ Hypotension [10]
 - 145 ○ Septic shock [10]
 - 146 ○ Elevated serum lactate : >2 mmol/L (18 mg/dL) [10]
 - 147 ○ Ileus
 - 148 ○ Toxic megacolon
 - 149 ○ Bowel perforation
 - 150 ○ Any fulminant course of disease (i.e. rapid deterioration of the patient).
 - 151 ● **Treatment response** has been clearly defined by the European society [4].
 - 152 ○ Resolution of diarrhea with maintenance of resolution for the duration of
153 therapy and at least 48 hours after the end of treatment, and no further
154 requirement for CDI therapy
 - 155 **AND**
 - 156 ○ Improvement of parameters of disease severity (clinical, laboratory,
157 radiological) and no new signs of severe disease
 - 158 Treatment response should be observed daily and evaluated after **at least 3 days**,
159 assuming that the patient is not worsening on treatment.
 - 160 ● **Recurrence** is defined as CDI recurrence **within 8 weeks** after complete resolution of
161 the initial episode. After 8 weeks, it is a new first episode.
 - 162 ● **Refractory CDI** is defined as a non-response to treatment after 3-5 days of therapy
163 (persistence of >3 loose stools, i.e. Bristol stool scale 6-7, in 24 hours). A refractory CDI
164 should prompt evaluation for co-infections or differential diagnostic, including non-
165 infectious diarrhea.

SSI recommendation for diagnosis

- 168 ● An episode of CDI is defined as clinical symptoms compatible with CDI with a
169 microbiologic confirmation ideally relying on a multistep algorithm.
- 170 ● Severe forms are defined by the presence of one of the following criteria: leukocytosis,
171 renal failure or core body temperature higher than 38.5°C .
- 172 ● Severe-complicated forms are defined by the occurrence of hypotension, septic shock,
173 elevated serum lactate, ileus, toxic megacolon, bowel perforation, or any fulminant
174 course.

177 **Risk Factors**

178 • **Risk factors**

179 The main factors identified as contributors to the development and severity of CDI are related
180 to microbiota disruption interventions such as exposure to systemic antibiotic use, exposure to
181 spores and alteration of the host immunity [17].

182 The risk resulting from systemic antibiotic differs according to the treatment duration, with the
183 shorter, the better[18] . Antibiotics have been categorized according to their risk of selecting *C.*
184 *difficile*, with high risk including clindamycin, fluoroquinolones, second generation cephalosporins
185 and higher, carbapenems, combinations of Beta-Lactamases and Beta-Lactamases Inhibitors (e.g.
186 piperacillin-tazobactam). Fluoroquinolone use was associated with a higher risk because of the
187 NAP1/BI/027 strain [18–20]. The risk associated to each antibiotic class is summarized in **Table**
188 **1**.

189 Seventy to eighty percent of CDI occur in adults aged ≥ 65 years [1]. Recurrences are more
190 frequently observed in older populations, affecting 20-30% of patients [21]. Over 80% of CDI-
191 related mortalities occur in individuals aged ≥ 75 years, particularly those with prior comorbidities,
192 hospitalizations, and frailty [21].

193 Systemic antibiotics are the strongest risk factor but are often unavoidable, other risk factors
194 include use of proton pump inhibitors and other acid-suppressing agents, which represent the next
195 strongest modifiable risk factors; prior healthcare exposure, including long-term care residency and
196 prolonged hospitalization; and host-related factors such as inadequate antibody responses to *C.*
197 *difficile* toxins, chemotherapy or corticosteroid use, severity of underlying illness, comorbidities,
198 immunosenescence, and reduced functional status. [22–24] . Prior *C. difficile* colonisation or
199 infection is also recognized as a significant risk factor [25,26] . All risk factors are summarized in
200 **Table 2**.

201

202 **Treatment**

203 • **General Measures [4] :**

- 204 ○ Stop unnecessary antibiotics.
- 205 ○ Rehydrate and correct electrolytes.
- 206 ○ Avoid antiperistaltic drugs.
- 207 ○ Reassess indication to proton pump inhibitor.
- 208 ○ Probiotics not recommended.

209 • **Drugs currently available:**

- 210 ○ **Metronidazole:** A multicenter randomized controlled trial compared
211 vancomycin and metronidazole [27]. Clinical success with metronidazole was
212 72.7%, inferior to vancomycin (81.1%) ($P = .02$). In severe CDI, metronidazole
213 clinical success was 66.3% vs 78.5% for vancomycin ($P = .059$). Post-hoc analysis
214 found lower odds of success with metronidazole compared with vancomycin;
215 factors favoring success overall included treatment-naive status and
216 mild/moderate disease. In a prospective cohort of 75 primary, uncomplicated
217 CDI patients [28], treatment with metronidazole was associated with
218 significantly higher recurrence: 40.9% vs 15.1% on univariate analysis and
219 remained an independent predictor in Cox regression (HR 3.27, 95% CI 1.31–
220 8.19). The authors concluded metronidazole should be avoided for primary
221 treatment, aligning with guidelines favoring vancomycin or fidaxomicin.
222 Network meta-analysis further confirmed that metronidazole is inferior to
223 vancomycin, and fidaxomicin for sustained symptomatic cure [29]. Initial
224 treatment failure rates are higher with metronidazole compared to vancomycin

225 (RR 1.58, 95% CI 1.10–2.27) [30]. These differences are more pronounced in
226 older patients, those with comorbidities, and those with severe disease, where
227 metronidazole is associated with higher risk of treatment failure, recurrence,
228 and mortality [6,31].

229 Finally, there is a documented rise in metronidazole resistance among *C. difficile*
230 isolates, including elevated minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) and
231 emergence of plasmid-mediated resistance, particularly in epidemic ribotypes
232 [32,33]. The pharmacokinetic profile of metronidazole is suboptimal: oral
233 administration results in low fecal concentrations, and its bioactivity is further
234 reduced by interaction with the gut microbiota [32,33]. This leads to
235 subinhibitory exposure, promoting bacterial adaptation and potential treatment
236 failure.

237 While metronidazole is substantially less expensive than vancomycin or
238 fidaxomicin, the inferior efficacy and increasing resistance outweigh its cost
239 advantage in most clinical scenarios. Cost-effectiveness analyses suggest that
240 lower recurrence rates with fidaxomicin and vancomycin may offset their higher
241 upfront costs[34].

242 The cumulative evidence from randomized trials, meta-analyses, and
243 antimicrobial resistance data supports removing metronidazole from the
244 routine treatment of CDI due to its lower efficacy, higher rates of treatment
245 failure and recurrence, rising resistance, suboptimal pharmacokinetics,
246 consistent with updated international guideline recommendations favoring
247 vancomycin and fidaxomicin.

248 ○ **Vancomycin and Fidaxomicin:** Following on international guideline
249 recommendations [4,7], recent meta-analyses and systematic reviews of
250 randomized controlled trials clarify the comparative efficacy and safety profile
251 of fidaxomicin over vancomycin in CDI. Pooled data from six randomized
252 controlled trials (RCTs) demonstrate that fidaxomicin yields significantly higher
253 global cure rates (risk ratio [RR] 1.18, $P < 0.00001$) and markedly lower
254 recurrence rates (RR 0.59, $P < 0.0001$) compared to vancomycin, while initial
255 clinical cure rates and adverse event profiles remain comparable between
256 agents [35]. These findings are consistent across diverse patient populations,
257 including those with non-severe and severe CDI, although the benefit in severe
258 CDI may be less pronounced and vancomycin may retain a slight advantage in
259 initial cure for severe cases [36]. Subgroup analyses indicate that the reduction
260 of recurrence rates with fidaxomicin is particularly relevant for older adults and
261 those with comorbidities, such as cancer or renal impairment, where recurrence
262 risk and healthcare utilization are highest [37]. Recently in a randomized
263 controlled open trial of hospitalized CDI patients receiving concomitant
264 antibiotics, clinical cure was numerically higher with fidaxomicin than
265 vancomycin (73% vs 62.9%) but not statistically significant. Recurrence within
266 30 days was rare and similar between groups (3.3% vs 4.0%; only 4 total rCDI
267 cases)[38]. Overall recurrence rate was lower than anticipated in both arms, the
268 global mortality reached 6.8% with no differences between the groups.

269 ○ **Extended administration regimens:**
270 Pulsed tapered administration of vancomycin is advocated in some guidelines
271 for specific situations. Meta-analytic data indicate that taper-and-pulse

272 regimens achieve higher resolution rates (83%) compared to taper alone (68%)
273 or pulse alone (54%) in recurrent CDI, though the evidence is limited by study
274 heterogeneity and small sample sizes [39,40] . A small case series provides a
275 long-term follow up of 20 patients treated by vancomycin 125mg qd for 8 weeks
276 from 2013-2017, confirming an efficient treatment, with only one relapse per
277 220 patients-months. However, among 13 patients discontinuing this
278 treatment, the same authors observed 31% (n=4) relapses in the 6 weeks
279 following treatment discontinuation [41] . A more recent RCT compared pulsed
280 tapered administration of vancomycin versus its standard dosing for a first
281 episode or a first recurrence of CDI among 12 Canadian hospitals, with 256
282 patients. Significant effect at day 38 shedded at day 56 (14.8% for taper pulse
283 vancomycine and 17.7% for standard dosing, with an aRR of 0.84 [0.48-1.45])
284 [42] . The AGA clinical practice guidelines propose this solution as alternative to
285 fecal microbiota-based therapies [43], the ESCMID suggest this option if the
286 preferred option is not available for first recurrences onward [4].

287
288 Extended-pulsed fidaxomicin regimens have also shown superior sustained cure
289 rates in older inpatients compared to standard vancomycin courses [44].
290 Economic evaluations consistently report that the higher acquisition cost of
291 fidaxomicin is offset by reduced recurrence and hospital readmission costs,
292 resulting in cost-effectiveness or cost savings in most analyses, especially among
293 high-risk subgroups and those receiving concomitant antibiotics [37] . Direct
294 cost studies confirm that fidaxomicin use is associated with lower hospital
295 admission-related expenses, supporting its economic value in routine clinical
296 practice. There are no randomized controlled trials directly comparing
297 pulsed/tapered vancomycin to fidaxomicin or other regimens for recurrent CDI,
298 and animal models suggest that pulsed dosing may not facilitate clearance of *C.*
299 *difficile* colonization [40] .

300 Focusing on the gut microbiota, the 2 regimens are however not comparable,
301 vancomycin, including pulsed regimens, causes profound and persistent
302 microbiota disruption with 2-4 log₁₀ reductions in key bacterial groups
303 (Bacteroides, Firmicutes), decreased diversity (26.2 vs 349.1 OTUs in mice), loss
304 of colonization resistance persisting 18 days post-treatment, and increased
305 susceptibility to VRE and multidrug-resistant organisms [45–48] . In contrast,
306 fidaxomicin preserves microbiota diversity (134.2 OTUs), maintains colonization
307 resistance, allows persistence of major microbiome components during
308 treatment, and promotes faster recovery with significantly higher Shannon
309 diversity through day 55 in clinical trials [44,46,47,49] .

310
311 ○ **Tigecycline** is not recommended as a first-line therapy for CDI, but available
312 evidence suggests it may be considered as an adjunctive or alternative option in
313 severe CDI when oral administration is not possible, and in refractory CDI [4].
314 Retrospective cohort studies and meta-analyses indicate that tigecycline may
315 improve clinical cure rates and reduce complicated disease courses in severe
316 CDI, but does not significantly impact mortality or relapse rates compared to
317 standard therapy [50–53]. Case reports and small series suggest safety and

318 efficacy in patients with severe, refractory CDI with rapid symptom
319 improvement and low recurrence rates[53,54].

320 In summary, tigecycline may be considered for severe, severe complicated, or
321 refractory CDI as adjunctive therapy [4], but is not supported for routine use in
322 initial or non-severe cases due to insufficient high-quality evidence.

323 ○ **Bezlotoxumab** (Zinplava) is discontinued and no longer available as of January
324 2025 because Merck, the manufacturer, discontinued the product.

325 ○ **Fecal microbiota transplantation** (FMT) is a highly effective therapy for recurrent
326 *Clostridioides difficile* infection (rCDI) compared to standard-of-care antibiotics.
327 Multiple randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses justify the use of fecal
328 microbiota transplantation (FMT) in rCDI. The landmark trial by van Nood et al.
329 demonstrated that FMT delivered via nasoduodenal tube after vancomycin
330 pretreatment resulted in cure rates of 81%, compared to 31% for vancomycin
331 alone and 23% for vancomycin plus bowel lavage, establishing FMT as superior
332 to antibiotics for rCDI [55]. A double-blind RCT by Kelly et al. found that donor
333 FMT via colonoscopy achieved clinical cure in 90.9% of patients with multiply
334 recurrent CDI, compared to 62.5% with autologous FMT (P = 0.042), with no
335 serious adverse events attributable to FMT [56]. A single-center RCT by Hvas et
336 al. showed FMT was superior to both fidaxomicin and vancomycin for rCDI, with
337 clinical resolution rates of 92% for FMT, 42% for fidaxomicin, and 19% for
338 vancomycin [57]. The Kao et al. RCT demonstrated noninferiority of oral capsule
339 FMT compared to colonoscopic FMT, with both modalities achieving high cure
340 rates for rCDI [58]. Real-world multicenter data confirm similar effectiveness for
341 capsule and colonoscopic FMT with cure rates of 81–86% at 1–2 months [59].
342 Meta-analyses and systematic reviews consistently report pooled cure rates of
343 76–92% for FMT in rCDI, with a number needed to treat (NNT) of 3 and no
344 significant increase in serious adverse events [60,61]. FMT is effective regardless
345 of delivery route or preparation, and capsule formulations are as effective as
346 colonoscopic delivery [58,59,62].

347 American as well as European societies recommend FMT for immunocompetent
348 adults with multiple recurrences of CDI, typically after failure of standard
349 antibiotic regimens such as vancomycin or fidaxomicin [4–6,43,63]. This is also
350 proposed in a recent review published by van Prehn et al. [3].

351 Emerging evidence supports the use of FMT in earlier stages of CDI, including
352 first recurrence and even first episode. A recent RCT demonstrated that FMT is
353 non-inferior to vancomycin for primary CDI with similar cure rates (78.4% vs.
354 61.2%, 95.2%CI: -0.7 to 35.1%) and no increase in adverse events [64]. In this
355 study FMT was performed without any prior antibiotic treatment. Another
356 double-blind, placebo-controlled trial found that FMT after vancomycin for first
357 or second CDI episode resulted in a 90% cure rate significantly higher than
358 placebo [65]. The American Gastroenterological Association notes that select
359 non-severely-immunocompromised patients at high risk for recurrence or with
360 severe/refractory disease may benefit from FMT after the initial episode or first
361 recurrence, though shared decision-making is recommended [43].

362 Cost-effectiveness analyses indicate that FMT is a cost-effective strategy for first
363 recurrent CDI with favorable incremental cost-effectiveness ratios and high
364 probability of cost-effectiveness at standard willingness-to-pay thresholds [66].

365 FMT is well tolerated with no significant difference in serious adverse events
366 compared to control and only minor, transient gastrointestinal symptoms
367 reported in most cases [67] .

368 Long-term follow-up studies, including prospective registry data with a median
369 follow-up of 30–44 months, show a low incidence of new-onset medical
370 conditions after FMT, with no clustering of diseases associated with dysbiosis
371 and no increased risk of inflammatory bowel disease, irritable bowel syndrome,
372 allergy, diabetes, or psychiatric disorders [68–71] . Most new diagnoses
373 reported in long-term studies were adjudicated as unlikely to be related to FMT.
374 Infectious complications are rare, especially with current donor screening
375 protocols, though isolated cases of transmission of multidrug-resistant
376 organisms have been reported, prompting enhanced regulatory oversight [72] .
377 In mildly or moderately immunocompromised patients, FMT appears to have a
378 safety and effectiveness profile comparable to immunocompetent populations,
379 with a serious adverse event rate of approximately 10% [43,73] .

380 In summary, FMT is strongly supported by randomized trials and major society
381 guidelines for multiple recurrent CDI, and emerging evidence supports its use in
382 first recurrence and select cases of initial CDI. FMT offers high efficacy, safety,
383 and cost-effectiveness, and should be considered as part of a patient-centered,
384 evidence-based approach to CDI management.

385 In Switzerland, FMT is considered as a drug, and the manufacturing therefore
386 requires a SwissMedic validation through a GMP process with a market
387 authorization. The CHUV in Lausanne is a SwissMedic certified center and FMT
388 is available (frozen capsules and liquid formulations) (Contact
389 min.tmf@chuv.ch).

390 • **Rationale for severe and severe complicated forms**

391 ○ **Severe CDI:** Recent meta-analyses and randomized controlled trials indicate that
392 fidaxomicin is non-inferior to vancomycin for initial clinical cure in severe CDI,
393 however, a 2024 meta-analysis found that vancomycin was statistically more
394 effective than fidaxomicin for severe CDI (risk ratio [RR] = 0.94, 95% CI: 0.90–
395 0.98, $P < .01$), though the absolute difference was modest [36] . Fidaxomicin
396 consistently demonstrates lower recurrence rates and improved long-term
397 mortality in general CDI populations, but these benefits are not clearly
398 established in severe CDI subgroups, with no significant difference in recurrence
399 rates between fidaxomicin and vancomycin for severe CDI specifically
400 [30,35,74] . In a large propensity-matched analysis, combined clinical failure or
401 recurrence rates were similar (fidaxomicin 31.9% vs vancomycin 25.5%, $P =$
402 0.071), as were 30-, 90-, and 180-day mortality rates [75] . When oral
403 administration is not possible, intravenous metronidazole or tigecycline can be
404 associated to vancomycin local delivery [4]

405 ○ **Complicated CDI:** Smaller retrospective studies in critically ill or fulminant CDI
406 patients treated with fidaxomicin report response rates comparable to those in
407 general medical wards, but sample sizes are limited and treatment failure rates
408 remain high [6] . As a result, most of the current recommendations are based
409 on expert opinions rather than strong experimental proofs. The majority of
410 clinical trials and real-world studies exclude fulminant CDI, leaving a significant
411 evidence gap for fidaxomicin in this population. For complicated CDI, defined by

412 hypotension, shock, ileus, or megacolon, oral vancomycin (500 mg four times
413 daily, with or without rectal administration) plus intravenous metronidazole 500
414 mg every 8 hours is recommended as first-line therapy for fulminant CDI; for
415 patients with ileus, rectal vancomycin (500 mg every 6 hours) should be added
416 to ensure adequate colonic drug delivery. Early surgical consultation is advised
417 for patients with clinical deterioration or evidence of toxic megacolon [4,7,43] .
418 Fidaxomicin has not been adequately studied in this population.

419 ○ **FMT in severe and complicated forms:** Clinical trial and cohort data support the
420 use of FMT in severe and complicated forms of CD), particularly when standard
421 medical therapy fails. In a retrospective analysis, sequential FMT combined with
422 vancomycin achieved cure in 100% of severe and 87% of fulminant CDI cases
423 during the same admission, and a randomized trial showed 100% success for
424 multiple FMTs plus vancomycin versus 75% for a single FMT plus vancomycin,
425 with no serious adverse events reported [76] .

426 Meta-analysis of 16 studies (including one randomized trial) found a pooled
427 clinical cure rate of 61% after a single FMT in severe/fulminant CDI, with major
428 adverse events in 10.9%, colectomy in 8.2%, and all-cause mortality of 15.6%
429 [77] . Observational studies report that FMT in severe/fulminant CDI reduces
430 mortality and colectomy rates compared to standard care, with a NNT of 2–3 to
431 prevent one death [78] . FMT can be safely administered via colonoscopy, even
432 in toxic megacolon, using careful technique [6] .

433 Most protocols recommend continuing anti-CDI antibiotics (vancomycin or
434 fidaxomicin) alongside FMT, and repeating FMT every 3–5 days until clinical and
435 endoscopic resolution [6] . Overall, FMT is effective and safe as salvage therapy
436 for severe and complicated CDI, with improved survival and low rates of serious
437 adverse events when performed with appropriate donor screening and
438 procedural precautions.

439

440 ● **Empirical Antibiotic Therapy:**

441 ○ Start if microbiological confirmation is delayed or in complicated CDI.

442 ○ Avoid empirical use of fidaxomicin.

443

444 ● **Confirmed CDI Treatment:**

445 The treatment of documented CDI varies according to the type of episode (first episode, first
446 recurrence, or multiple recurrences), the presence of risk factors for recurrence, and disease
447 severity. For a first episode, the standard first-line therapy is fidaxomicin, as an alternative
448 second-line option, vancomycin may be used. In patients with risk factors for recurrence,
449 fidaxomicin is preferred for the initial episode because of its lower recurrence risk. For a first
450 recurrence, treatment depends on prior therapy: if fidaxomicin was used initially, vancomycin
451 is recommended, whereas fidaxomicin can be used if vancomycin was given during the first
452 episode. All these choices are in line with the current European recommendations [4] . For
453 second or subsequent recurrences, fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) is recommended. If
454 the preferred options are unavailable, alternatives include vancomycin for an initial episode
455 and vancomycin taper-and-pulse regimens for recurrent disease.

456 Management also depends on disease severity. In severe CDI with oral treatment possible,
457 either fidaxomicin or vancomycin is recommended as first-line therapy, with FMT considered
458 through multidisciplinary decision-making. If oral therapy is not possible, local delivery of

459 vancomycin combined with intravenous metronidazole or tigecycline may be used. In severe-
460 complicated CDI, treatment includes local vancomycin delivery with intravenous metronidazole
461 or tigecycline, and escalation to surgical management or fecal microbiota transplantation may
462 be required following multidisciplinary evaluation.

463 The algorithm based on severity, risk factor for recurrence, type of episode is depicted in **Figure**
464 **2**.

465

466 **New drugs**

467 There are two microbiota-derived standardized live biotherapeutic products (LBPs) treatments
468 licensed for CDI. Both FDA-approved products (SER-109 and RBX2660) demonstrated
469 substantial reduction recurrence risk in rCDI compared with placebo, with recurrence rates of
470 ~12% vs 40% and treatment success rates of ~71% versus ~58%, respectively.

471 • SER-109 (VOWST™) are fecal viable Firmicutes spores (purified suspension from healthy
472 donors) that are applied orally four capsules daily for three consecutive days. SER-109 is
473 FDA-approved since 2023 for prevention of recurrent CDI in adults with rCDI after antibiotic
474 treatment. In a randomized, placebo-controlled Phase III, trial (ECOSPOR III), orally applied
475 SER-109 (4 capsules daily for 3 days) demonstrated superiority over placebo in reducing the
476 risk of rCDI. The proportion of patients with rCDI up to 8 weeks after dosing was 12% in the
477 SER-109 group compared with 40% in the placebo group. The relative risk (RR) of recurrence
478 was 0.32 (95% CI, 0.18–0.58) for SER-109 vs. placebo (P<0.001) [79]. Engraftment was rapid
479 and correlated with favorable outcomes. Post-hoc analyses showed lower risks regardless
480 of baseline characteristics, comorbidities, co-medications and ribotype [80].

481 • RBX2660 (REBYOTA™) are cryopreserved broad consortia of live microbes from screened
482 healthy donors, applied rectally as a single dose microbiota suspension (150 ml). RBX2660
483 is FDA-approved since 2022 for prevention of recurrent CDI in adults with rCDI after
484 antibiotic treatment.

485 In a randomized controlled, double-blind, placebo-controlled Phase 3 trial, a single-dose
486 enema of RBX2660 achieved treatment success rates of 70.6% versus 57.5% for placebo at
487 8 weeks with an estimated treatment effect of 13.1% and a posterior probability of
488 superiority of 0.991 [81]. There were more side effects with RBX2660 but most were mild
489 gastrointestinal disorders such as diarrhea and abdominal pain and overall safety was good.

490 One further LBP has received orphan drug designation from FDA for CDI treatment:

491 • VE303 (Vedanta Biosciences®) is a defined bacterial consortium composed of 8 well-
492 characterized, nonpathogenic, nontoxigenic, commensal strains of *Clostridia*, administered
493 orally in capsules. FDA has granted VE303 Orphan Drug designation for the prevention of
494 rCDI in individuals with prior rCDI. A phase 2, double-blind, placebo-controlled dose-ranging
495 study in adults with laboratory-confirmed CDI showed a significantly reduced risk of
496 recurrence of 13.8% for high-dose VE303 versus 45.5% for placebo. This equates to an
497 adjusted absolute risk reduction (ARR) of 30.5% (P =0.006) [82]. A Phase 3 study of VE303
498 for patients with rCDI is currently recruiting.

499 A comparison of the efficacy of these LBPs compared to classic FMT from the pivotal van Nood
500 trial is presented in **Figure 3**.

501 Other investigational microbiota-derived oral therapeutics include MET-2 and VP20621, which
502 have been tested in phase-1 studies but to date still lack clinical efficacy data from clinical trials.
503 All these products offer consistent composition and rigorous safety screening, addressing
504 limitations of conventional FMT. There are no head-to-head trial data available of these new
505 products against FMT and none have been approved by EMA or Swissmedic. Current

506 international guidelines do not include these novel compounds yet. Therefore, we await further
507 data and approval before we can make recommendations for their use.
508
509

510 **SSI recommendation for treatment**

- 511 • Fidaxomicin is the first line treatment for first episode
- 512 • In the absence of risk factors for recurrence, vancomycin can be proposed as an
513 alternative
- 514 • In severe episodes, vancomycin and fidaxomicin can both be proposed
- 515 • In severe complicated forms and when oral administration is not possible, vancomycin
516 local delivery associated to metronidazole or tigecycline intravenously is proposed
- 517 • Fecal microbiota transplantation is recommended after the second recurrence but
518 several lines of evidence suggest a potential role earlier.
- 519 • Live biotherapeutics products are not yet recommended

520
521

522 **Prevention & Infection control**

- 523 • **Primary prevention of *C. difficile* infection**

524 We concur with the Clinical Practice Guidelines for Clostridium difficile Infection in Adults and
525 Children: 2017 Update by the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) and Society for
526 Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA) [5], that there is insufficient evidence to
527 recommend administration of probiotics for primary prevention of CDI at this point

- 528 • **Prevention of *C. difficile* transmission in healthcare settings**

529 **Table 3** provides an overview of recommendations on infection prevention and control
530 measures to prevent transmission of *C. difficile* in healthcare settings. These recommendations
531 are based on the Guidance document for prevention of CDI in acute healthcare settings
532 published on behalf of the European society of clinical microbiology and infectious diseases
533 (ESCMID) [83]. In general, these measures are supported by the Clinical Practice Guidelines
534 for Clostridium difficile Infection in Adults and Children: 2017 Update by the Infectious Diseases
535 Society of America (IDSA) and Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA) [5], in
536 part with differing strengths of recommendations and quality assessments.
537 Further details are beyond the scope of this guideline.

538

539 **Note:** For initial fidaxomicin prescription a contact with the patient insurance company may be
540 required because currently, reimbursement is limited to specific situations: no response to
541 metronidazole and vancomycin, or multiple recurrences (≥ 2), or follow-up treatment of
542 patients who were previously treated as inpatients with fidaxomicin. These limitations are not
543 in line with the current literature.

544
545

546
547
548
549
550
551
552
553
554
555
556
557
558
559
560

Figure legends

Figure 1: Diagnostic approach of *Clostridioides difficile* infection

Figure 2: Suggested treatment algorithm for *Clostridioides difficile* infection.

*Consider Extended fidaxomicin: 200mg bid on day 1-5, 200mg q48h on day 7-25

**Can be discussed earlier in selected patients. FMT is always performed after a full 10 days treatment of vancomycin or fidaxomicin

§Vancomycin taper pulse: 2 weeks 125mg qid, 1 week 125mg bid, 1 week 125mg qd, 1 week 125mg q48h, 1 week 125mg q72h

£In multiple recurrences, vancomycin taper pulse is extremely less effective than FMT and should be considered only if FMT is not available

££If one risk factor for recurrence is present

Figure 3: Efficacy of RBX2660, SER109, and VE303 compared to classic FMT.

Table 1: Antibiotic-specific risk for *Clostridioides difficile* infection in outpatient and inpatient settings, complemented by pharmaco-epidemiological data (FEARS database) [20,84–86].

Antibiotic class		Antibiotic name (Risk)	Estimates	Source
Penicillins	Non-antistaphylococcal	Amoxicillin (L)	OR : 1.96 [95%CI 1.88–2.04]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 6.74 [95%CI 5.92–7.67]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
		Penicillin (L)	OR : 1.8 [95%CI 1.59–2.03]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 2.91 [95%CI 1.09–7.77]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Antistaphylococcal	Flucloxacillin	ROR : 56.08 [95%CI 22.13–142.10]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Beta Lactamases inhibitor combinations	Amoxicillin/clavulanate (H)	OR : 8.53 [95%CI 8.23–8.85]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 16.84 [95%CI 15.01–18.89]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
		Piperacillin/tazobactam (H)	OR : 6.99 [95%CI 1.81–27.02]	Outpatients [1]
ROR : 17.35 [95%CI 15.30–19.69]			Pharmacovigilance [3]	
Céphalosporins	1st generation	Cefazolin (L)	OR : 2.3 [95%CI 1.9-2.6]	Inpatients
			ROR : 17.26 [95%CI 13.30–22.39]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	2nd generation	Cefuroxime (H)	OR : 9.59 [95%CI 8.79–10.45]	Outpatients [1]
			OR : 6.4 [95%CI 5.1-7.9]	Inpatients [2]
			ROR : 15.03 [95%CI 13.02–17.37]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	3d generation	Cefpodoxime (H)	OR : 9.17 [95%CI 6.99–12.04]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 37.3 [95%CI 25.54–54.49]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
		Ceftriaxone (H)	OR : 6.93 [95%CI 5.16–9.29]	Outpatients [1]
			OR : 4.0 [95%CI 3.5-4.6]	Inpatients [2]
			ROR : 10.07 [95%CI 8.80–11.53]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
		Ceftazidime	ROR : 21.31 [95%CI 14.86–30.56]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	3d generation + BLIs	Ceftazidime/Avibactam	ROR : 8.24 [95%CI 4.26–15.93]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
		Ceftolozane/Tazobactam	ROR : 5.89 [95%CI 3.05–11.38]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	4th generation	Cefepime (M)	OR : 4.45 [95%CI 1.18–16.80]	Outpatients [1]
			OR : 2.8 [95%CI 2.1-3.6]	Inpatients [2]
ROR : 12.51 [95%CI 9.30–16.83]			Pharmacovigilance [3]	

	5th generation	Ceftaroline	ROR : 5.29 [95%CI 1.98–14.19]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
Carbapenems	Meropenem (H)		OR : 5.1 [4.4-6.0]	Inpatients [2]
			OR : 3.31 [95%CI 0.81–13.61]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 16.46 [95%CI 13.65–19.85]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Imipenem/Cilastatin (H)		OR : 5.1 [4.4-6.0]	Inpatients [2]
			ROR : 12.23 [95%CI 9.77–15.32]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Ertapenem (M)		OR : 3.51 [95%CI 1.47–8.40]	Outpatients [1]
		OR : 2.5 [95%CI 2.0-3.2]	Inpatients [2]	
		ROR : 10.77 [95%CI 8.51–13.63]	Pharmacovigilance [3]	
Lincosamides	Clindamycin (H)		OR : 25.39 [95%CI 24.11–26.72]	Outpatients [1]
			OR : 1.9 [95%CI 1.5-2.5]	Inpatients [2]
			ROR : 30.41 [95%CI 28.24-32.75]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
Fluoroquinolones	Ciprofloxacin (H)		OR : 6.83 [95%CI 6.56–7.1]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 8.82 [95%CI 8.16–9.54]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Moxifloxacin (M)		OR : 4.71 [95%CI 4.14–5.37]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 8.08 [95%CI 7.25–9.01]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Levofloxacin (L)		OR : 2.49 [95%CI 2.35–2.64]	Outpatients [1]
		ROR : 4.12 [95%CI 3.71–4.59]	Pharmacovigilance [3]	
	Norfloxacin		ROR : 13.2 [95%CI 7.43–23.43]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
Aminoglycosides	Tobramycin (M)		OR : 4.2 [95%CI 1.32–13.39]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 1.05 [95%CI 0.67–1.62]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Amikacin		ROR : 13.04 [95%CI 6.95–24.46]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Gentamicin (L)		OR : 2.73 [95%CI 1.17–6.37]	Outpatients [1]
		ROR : 10.61 [95%CI 7.90–14.27]	Pharmacovigilance [3]	
Macrolides	Clarithromycin (L)		OR : 1.83 [95%CI 1.62–2.07]	Outpatients [1]
			ROR : 5.46 [95%CI 4.73–6.29]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Erythromycin (L)		OR : 1.53 [95%CI 1.21–1.93]	Outpatients [1]
		ROR : 4.34 [95%CI 3.20–5.88]	Pharmacovigilance [3]	
	Azithromycin (L)		OR : 1.31 [95%CI 1.26–1.37]	Outpatients [1]

		ROR : 2.71 [95%CI 2.27–3.24]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
Tetracyclines	Doxycycline (L)	OR : 0.96 [95%CI 0.89–1.02]	Outpatients [1]
		ROR : 2.96 [95%CI 2.35–3.71]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Minocycline (L)	OR : 0.79 [95%CI 0.67–0.93]	Outpatients [1]
Other	Cefiderocol	ROR : 17.25 [95%CI 6.36–46.84]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Fosfomycin (H)	OR : 5.68 [95%CI 2.89–11.17]	Outpatients [1]
		ROR : 16.37 [95%CI 10.89–24.61]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Metronidazole	ROR : 15.18 [95%CI 13.85–16.64]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Colistin	ROR : 6.39 [95%CI 2.38–17.13]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Tigecycline	ROR : 6.62 [95%CI 4.72–9.28]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Linezolid (M)	OR : 3.58 [95%CI 2.36–5.44]	Outpatients [1]
		OR : 1.2 [95%CI 1.0-1.5]	Inpatients [2]
		ROR : 2.28 [95%CI 1.79–2.92]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Sulfamethoxazole/Trimethoprim (L)	OR : 2.16 [95%CI 2.05–2.27]	Outpatients [1]
		OR : 2.0 [95%CI 1.6-2.6]	Inpatients [2]
		ROR : 4.43 [95%CI 3.55–5.51]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Nitrofurantoin (L)	OR : 1.77 [95%CI 1.65–1.89]	Outpatients [1]
		ROR : 1.55 [95%CI 0.83–2.88]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
	Vancomycin	ROR : 3.98 [95%CI 3.39–4.66]	Pharmacovigilance [3]
Daptomycin (L)	OR : 0.4 [95%CI 0.2-0.6]	Inpatients [2]	
	ROR : 2.05 [95%CI 1.46–2.87]	Pharmacovigilance [3]	
Aztreonam	ROR : 1.24 [95%CI 0.84–1.82]	Pharmacovigilance [3]	

Footnotes: Antibiotic classes and their respective agents are ranked according to their association with *C. difficile* infection, first in inpatient, then in outpatients settings. Reported Odds Ratios from pharmaco-epidemiological studies (FEARS database) are included as supplementary information for both settings. Results might differ with data derived from in-vitro susceptibilities, due to potential confounding exposure, including duration of treatment, IV/PO formulation, co-treatment, and regional variation/molecular shifts (NAP027). However, this table might provide pragmatic evidence that may guide antibiotic selection in either outpatient or inpatient setting. The risk is classified as high, moderate or low: **(H)**: high risk [defined as inpatient OR or outpatient OR >5], **(M)**: moderate risk [defined as inpatient OR or outpatient OR between 3–5], **(L)**: low risk [defined as inpatient OR or outpatient OR <3] , Blank: no inpatient/outpatient data.

Table 2: Risk factors for primary CDI, recurrent CDI, and outcomes. ✓ Means the risk factor is preventable, ✗ means that the risk factor is not preventable.

Risk category	Preventable	Risk factor	Evidence / effect size*	Notes & References
Microbiota disruption	✓	Systemic antibiotics	OR range ~3.55 (95% CI 2.56–4.94) compared to no antibiotics.	Association strength depends on antimicrobial classes, cumulated antibiotic exposure (duration, recurrence) [87,88] . C.f. Table 1 Underlying indication (e.g., severe illness) may confound [89,90] . Dose and duration matters [91] . Association disappears when only looking at RCTs (bias control, but shorter use & underpowered) [92,93]. Demonstrated a lower risk than PPIs [89] .
	✓	Proton pump inhibitors	aOR range ~1.14-4.50 in hospital populations. Risk: 36/1'000 persons [89] .	
	✓	H2-receptor antagonist	aOR range ~0.98-3.0 in hospital populations. Risk : 26/1'000 persons [89] .	
Spore exposure	✗	Prior <i>C. difficile</i> colonisation or infection	[25,26]	Also reflects healthcare-associated risk. Trajectory (ICU > wards) and length of stay (risk +1.3% per day) matters [84] .
	✗	Prior hospitalisation / prior-care facility residence	OR 2.18 [95%CI 1.86-2.56]: prior hospitalization in the last 6 months [94] .	
Host immunity	✗	Age ≥ 65 years	One of the most consistent risk factors. RR ~1.63 (95% CI 1.24–2.14) for rCDI	Probably due to immunosenescence. Age is non-modifiable but helps stratify risk [90] .
	✓	Chemotherapy in the prior month [22,95,96]		Also reflects disruption of the mucosal barrier. But may also reflect non-CDI diarrhea [97] .
	✓	Steroids [22–24]	Risk factor for CA- and complicated <i>C. difficile</i> infection (OR 2.09) and rCDI (2.45)	
	✗	Comorbidities	Haematological malignancy (OR range ~1.74-12.9), chronic liver diseases (OR range ~1.30-1.34), chronic kidney disease (OR range ~1.58-1.93), cardiovascular diseases .[26,90]	Cumulative effect of comorbidities on the risk, that may also reflects increased healthcare exposure.

Risk category	Preventable	Risk factor	Evidence / effect size*	Notes & References
Poor outcomes / severity / mortality	✓	Prolonged exposure to antibiotics prior to CDI [98]		
	✗	Advanced age [98,99]	Older age consistently shown to raise mortality risk.	Combined with comorbidities increases risk further [90] .
	✗	Male gender [100]		
	✗	Neutropenia [100]		
	✗	Multiple comorbidities (e.g., liver disease, kidney disease, cardiovascular disease)	Identified as likely risk factors for both primary and recurrent CDI.	Indicator of reduced physiological reserve [90] .
	✗	Hospital/ICU stay [98]	ICU stay associated with increased mortality in CDI cohorts.	Reflects severity of underlying illness and exposure [90] .
	✗	Severe form of CDI, <i>C. difficile</i> ribotype 078 [101]		

Table 3: Overview of recommendations on infection prevention and control measures to prevent transmission of *C. difficile* in healthcare settings

	Endemic setting		Outbreak setting	
Infection control measure	Recommendation	Quality of evidence	Recommendation	Quality of evidence
Surveillance in combination with timely feedback	Yes/Strong	Very low	Yes/Strong	Very low
Screening of asymptomatic patients	No/Conditional	Low	No/Conditional	Not applicable
Hand hygiene				
Switch from hand rub to hand washing	No/Conditional	Very low	Yes/Conditional	Very low
Increase compliance	Yes/Conditional	Very low	Yes/Conditional	Very low
Use of personal protective equipment (gloves/gowns)	Yes/Conditional	Very low	Yes/Strong	Very low
Implement contact precautions	Yes/Strong**	Very low	Yes/Strong	Very low
Environmental cleaning/disinfection				
Daily and terminal environmental sporicidal disinfection	Yes/Conditional	Very low	Yes/Strong	Very low
No touch disinfection systems	Yes/Conditional	Very low	Yes/Conditional	Very low
Antibiotic Stewardship				
Restriction of antibiotic agents/classes	Yes/Strong	Moderate	Yes/Strong	Low
Reducing the duration of antibiotic therapy	Yes/Strong	Very low	Yes/Strong	Very low
Education				
Of healthcare workers	Yes/Strong	Very low	Yes/Strong	Not applicable
Of patients and visitors	Yes/Strong	Not applicable	Yes/Strong	Not applicable

**The authors acknowledge that institutions may choose to forgo contact precaution measures, providing strict surveillance of CDI rates and implementation of other prevention

References

- [1] Leffler DA, Lamont JT. Clostridium difficile Infection. N Engl J Med 2015;372:1539–48. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmra1403772>.
- [2] Smits WK, Garey KW, Riley TV, et al. Clostridioides difficile should be considered a bacterial priority pathogen. Lancet Microbe 2025;101184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanmic.2025.101184>.
- [3] Prehn J van, Kuijper EJ, Dubberke ER. Recurrent Clostridioides difficile Infections. JAMA 2025;334. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2025.18089>.
- [4] Prehn J van, Reigadas E, Vogelzang EH, et al. European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases: 2021 update on the treatment guidance document for Clostridioides difficile infection in adults. Clin Microbiol Infec 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2021.09.038>.
- [5] McDonald LC, Gerding DN, Johnson S, et al. Clinical Practice Guidelines for Clostridium difficile Infection in Adults and Children: 2017 Update by the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) and Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA). Clin Infect Dis 2018;66:e1–48. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/cix1085>.
- [6] Kelly CR, Fischer M, Allegretti JR, et al. ACG Clinical Guidelines: Prevention, Diagnosis, and Treatment of Clostridioides difficile Infections. Am J Gastroenterol 2021;116:1124–47. <https://doi.org/10.14309/ajg.0000000000001278>.
- [7] Johnson S, Lavergne V, Skinner AM, et al. Clinical Practice Guideline by the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) and Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA): 2021 Focused Update Guidelines on Management of Clostridioides difficile Infection in Adults. Clin Infect Dis 2021;73:755–7. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab718>.
- [8] Hoffmann DE, Javitt GH, Kelly CR, et al. Fecal microbiota transplantation: a tale of two regulatory pathways. Gut Microbes 2025;17:2493901. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19490976.2025.2493901>.
- [9] Knoop FC, Owens M, Crocker IC. Clostridium difficile: clinical disease and diagnosis. Clin Microbiol Rev 1993;6:251–65. <https://doi.org/10.1128/cmr.6.3.251>.
- [10] Singer M, Deutschman CS, Seymour CW, et al. The Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock (Sepsis-3). Jama, vol. 315, 2016, p. 801–810. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2016.0287>.
- [11] Miller JM, Binnicker MJ, Campbell S, et al. Guide to Utilization of the Microbiology Laboratory for Diagnosis of Infectious Diseases: 2024 Update by the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) and the American Society for Microbiology (ASM) *. Clin Infect Dis 2024:ciae104. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciae104>.

- [12] Freeman J, Wilcox MH. The effects of storage conditions on viability of *Clostridium difficile* vegetative cells and spores and toxin activity in human faeces. *Journal of Clinical Pathology* 2003;56:126-128.
- [13] Schora DM, Peterson LR, Usacheva EA. Immunological Stability of *Clostridium difficile* Toxins in Clinical Specimens. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiology* 2018;39:434–8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ice.2018.20>.
- [14] Crobach MJ, Planche T, Eckert C, et al. European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases: update of the diagnostic guidance document for *Clostridium difficile* infection. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2016;22 Suppl 4:S63-81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2016.03.010>.
- [15] Senchyna F, Gaur RL, Gombar S, et al. *Clostridium difficile* PCR Cycle Threshold Predicts Free Toxin. *J Clin Microbiol* 2017;55:2651–60. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.00563-17>.
- [16] Crobach MJT, Duszenko N, Terveer EM, et al. Nucleic Acid Amplification Test Quantitation as Predictor of Toxin Presence in *Clostridium difficile* Infection. *J Clin Microbiol* 2018;56:95. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.01316-17>.
- [17] Asempa TE, Nicolau DP. *Clostridium difficile* infection in the elderly: an update on management. *Clin Interv Aging* 2017;12:1799–809. <https://doi.org/10.2147/cia.s149089>.
- [18] Gilboa M, Regev-Yochay G, Meltzer E, et al. Antibiotic Use and the Risk of Hospital-Onset *Clostridioides Difficile* Infection. *JAMA Netw Open* 2025;8:e2525252. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2025.25252>.
- [19] Vardakas KZ, Konstantelias AA, Loizidis G, et al. Risk factors for development of *Clostridium difficile* infection due to BI/NAP1/027 strain: a meta-analysis. *Int J Infect Dis* 2012;16:e768–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2012.07.010>.
- [20] Miller AC, Arakkal AT, Sewell DK, et al. Comparison of Different Antibiotics and the Risk for Community-Associated *Clostridioides difficile* Infection: A Case–Control Study. *Open Forum Infect Dis* 2023;10:ofad413. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ofid/ofad413>.
- [21] Esme M, Topeli A, Yavuz BB, et al. Infections in the Elderly Critically-Ill Patients. *Front Med* 2019;6:118. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2019.00118>.
- [22] Furuya-Kanamori L, Stone JC, Clark J, et al. Comorbidities, Exposure to Medications, and the Risk of Community-Acquired *Clostridium difficile* Infection: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiology* 2015;36:132–41. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ice.2014.39>.
- [23] Morrison RH, Hall NS, Said M, et al. Risk Factors Associated With Complications and Mortality in Patients With *Clostridium difficile* Infection. *Clin Infect Dis* 2011;53:1173–8. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/cir668>.
- [24] Messick CA, Hammel JP, Hull T. Risk Factors that Predict Recurrent *Clostridium difficile* Infections in Surgical Patients. *Am Surg* 2017;83:653–9.

- [25] D'Agostino SrRB, Collins SH, Pencina KM, et al. Risk estimation for recurrent *Clostridium difficile* infection based on clinical factors. *Clin Infect Dis* 2014;58:1386–93. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciu107>.
- [26] Rossen TM van, Ooijevaar RE, Vandenbroucke-Grauls CMJE, et al. Prognostic factors for severe and recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* infection: a systematic review. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2022;28:321–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2021.09.026>.
- [27] Johnson S, Louie TJ, Gerding DN, et al. Vancomycin, metronidazole, or tolevamer for *Clostridium difficile* infection: results from two multinational, randomized, controlled trials. *Clin Infect Dis* 1 AD;59:345–54. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciu313>.
- [28] Allegretti JR, Marcus J, Storm M, et al. Clinical Predictors of Recurrence After Primary *Clostridioides difficile* Infection: A Prospective Cohort Study. *Digest Dis Sci* 2020;65:1761–6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10620-019-05900-3>.
- [29] Beinortas T, Burr NE, Wilcox MH, et al. Comparative efficacy of treatments for *Clostridium difficile* infection: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2018;18:1035–44. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099\(18\)30285-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099(18)30285-8).
- [30] Stabholz Y, Paul M. The effect of antibiotic therapy for *Clostridioides difficile* infection on mortality and other patient-relevant outcomes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2024;30:51–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2023.09.002>.
- [31] Stevens VW, Nelson RE, Schwab-Daugherty EM, et al. Comparative Effectiveness of Vancomycin and Metronidazole for the Prevention of Recurrence and Death in Patients With *Clostridium difficile* Infection. *Jama Intern Med* 2017;177:546 8. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2016.9045>.
- [32] Doan T-H-D, Yen-Nicolaÿ S, Bernet-Camard M-F, et al. Impact of subinhibitory concentrations of metronidazole on proteome of *Clostridioides difficile* strains with different levels of susceptibility. *PLoS ONE* 2020;15:e0241903. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0241903>.
- [33] Krutova M, Wilcox M, Kuijper JE. *Clostridioides difficile* infection: are the three currently used antibiotic treatment options equal from pharmacological and microbiological points of view? *Int J Infect Dis* 2022;124:118–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2022.09.013>.
- [34] Burton HE, Mitchell SA, Watt M. A Systematic Literature Review of Economic Evaluations of Antibiotic Treatments for *Clostridium difficile* Infection. *Pharmacoeconomics* 2017;35:1123–40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40273-017-0540-2>.
- [35] Tashiro S, Mihara T, Sasaki M, et al. Oral fidaxomicin versus vancomycin for the treatment of *Clostridioides difficile* infection: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *J Infect Chemother* 2022;28:1536–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiac.2022.08.008>.
- [36] Zhao Z, Wu Y, Geng X, et al. Efficacy of fidaxomicin versus vancomycin in the treatment of *Clostridium difficile* infection: A systematic meta-analysis. *Medicine* 2024;103:e39213. <https://doi.org/10.1097/md.00000000000039213>.

- [37] Li Q, Obi E, Marciniak A, et al. Clinical and economic outcomes associated with fidaxomicin in comparison to vancomycin, metronidazole, and FMT: A systematic literature review. *Medicine* 2024;103:e39219. <https://doi.org/10.1097/md.00000000000039219>.
- [38] Rao K, Zhao Q, Bell J, et al. An Open-Label, Randomized Trial Comparing Fidaxomicin With Oral Vancomycin for the Treatment of *Clostridioides difficile* Infection in Hospitalized Patients Receiving Concomitant Antibiotics for Concurrent Infections. *Clin Infect Dis* 2023:ciad606. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciad606>.
- [39] Sehgal K, Zandvakili I, Tariq R, et al. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis: Efficacy of Vancomycin Taper and Pulse Regimens in *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Expert Rev Anti-Infect Ther* 2022;20:577–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14787210.2022.1997588>.
- [40] Pearlmutter BS, Carlisle MG, Wilson BM, et al. Pulsed dosing and extended daily dosing of oral vancomycin do not facilitate clearance of *Clostridioides difficile* colonization in mice. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 2023;68:e00903-23. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.00903-23>.
- [41] Zhang K, Beckett P, Abouanaser S, et al. Prolonged oral vancomycin for secondary prophylaxis of relapsing *Clostridium difficile* infection. *Bmc Infect Dis* 2014;19:51. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-019-3676-1>.
- [42] McDonald EG, Butler-Laporte G, Brophy JM, et al. Initial Vancomycin Taper for the Prevention of Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *JAMA Netw Open* 2026;9:e2560495. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2025.60495>.
- [43] Peery AF, Kelly CR, Kao D, et al. AGA Clinical Practice Guideline on Fecal Microbiota–Based Therapies for Select Gastrointestinal Diseases. *Gastroenterology* 2024;166:409–34. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2024.01.008>.
- [44] Guery B, Menichetti F, Anttila V-J, et al. Extended-pulsed fidaxomicin versus vancomycin for *Clostridium difficile* infection in patients 60 years and older (EXTEND): a randomised, controlled, open-label, phase 3b/4 trial. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2018;18:296–307. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099\(17\)30751-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099(17)30751-x).
- [45] Tomas ME, Mana TSC, Wilson BM, et al. Tapering Courses of Oral Vancomycin Induce Persistent Disruption of the Microbiota That Provide Colonization Resistance to *Clostridium difficile* and Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci in Mice. *Antimicrob Agents Ch* 2018;62:e02237-17. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.02237-17>.
- [46] Louie TJ, Cannon K, Byrne B, et al. Fidaxomicin Preserves the Intestinal Microbiome During and After Treatment of *Clostridium difficile* Infection (CDI) and Reduces Both Toxin Reexpression and Recurrence of CDI. *Clin Infect Dis* 1 AD;55:S132–42. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/cis338>.
- [47] Yamaguchi T, Konishi H, Aoki K, et al. The gut microbiome diversity of *Clostridioides difficile*-inoculated mice treated with vancomycin and fidaxomicin. *J Infect Chemother* 2020;26:483–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiac.2019.12.020>.
- [48] Deshpande A, Hurless K, Cadnum JL, et al. Effect of Fidaxomicin versus Vancomycin on Susceptibility to Intestinal Colonization with Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci and

Klebsiella pneumoniae in Mice. Antimicrob Agents Ch 2016;60:3988–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.02590-15>.

[49] Ajami NJ, Cope JL, Wong MC, et al. Impact of Oral Fidaxomicin Administration on the Intestinal Microbiota and Susceptibility to Clostridium difficile Colonization in Mice. Antimicrob Agents Ch 2018;62:e02112-17. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.02112-17>.

[50] Szabo BG, Kadar B, Lenart KS, et al. Use of intravenous tigecycline in patients with severe Clostridium difficile infection: a retrospective observational cohort study. Clin Microbiol Infec 2016;22:990–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2016.08.017>.

[51] Kechagias KS, Chorepsima S, Triarides NA, et al. Tigecycline for the treatment of patients with Clostridium difficile infection: an update of the clinical evidence. Eur J Clin Microbiol 2020;39:1053–8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10096-019-03756-z>.

[52] Phillips EC, Warren CA, Ma JZ, et al. Impact of Tigecycline on C. difficile Outcomes: Case Series and Propensity-Matched Retrospective Study. Antimicrob Agents Chemother 2022;66:e00001-22. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.00001-22>.

[53] Larson KC, Belliveau PP, Spooner LM. Tigecycline for the Treatment of Severe Clostridium difficile Infection. Ann Pharmacother 2011;45:1005–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1345/aph.1q080>.

[54] Herpers BL, Vlamincx B, Burkhardt O, et al. Intravenous Tigecycline as Adjunctive or Alternative Therapy for Severe Refractory Clostridium difficile Infection. Clin Infect Dis 2009;48:1732–5. <https://doi.org/10.1086/599224>.

[55] Nood E van, Vrieze A, Nieuwdorp M, et al. Duodenal infusion of donor feces for recurrent Clostridium difficile. New Engl J Medicine 2013;368:407–15.
<https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa1205037>.

[56] Kelly CR, Khoruts A, Staley C, et al. Effect of Fecal Microbiota Transplantation on Recurrence in Multiply Recurrent Clostridium difficile Infection: A Randomized Trial. Ann Intern Med 2013;159:609–16. <https://doi.org/10.7326/m13-0271>.

[57] Hvas CL, Jorgensen SMD, Jorgensen SP, et al. Fecal Microbiota Transplantation Is Superior to Fidaxomicin for Treatment of Recurrent Clostridium difficile Infection. Gastroenterology 2019;156:1324-1332 e3. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2018.12.019>.

[58] Kao D, Roach B, Silva M, et al. Effect of Oral Capsule- vs Colonoscopy-Delivered Fecal Microbiota Transplantation on Recurrent Clostridium difficile Infection. Jama 2017;318:1985–92. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.17077>.

[59] Vaughn BP, Fischer M, Kelly CR, et al. Effectiveness and Safety of Colonic and Capsule Fecal Microbiota Transplantation for Recurrent Clostridioides difficile Infection. Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol 2023;21:1330-1337.e2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cgh.2022.09.008>.

[60] Minkoff NZ, Aslam S, Medina M, et al. Fecal microbiota transplantation for the treatment of recurrent Clostridioides difficile (Clostridium difficile). Cochrane Database Syst Rev 2023;2023:CD013871. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd013871.pub2>.

- [61] Quraishi MN, Widlak M, Bhala N, et al. Systematic review with meta-analysis: the efficacy of faecal microbiota transplantation for the treatment of recurrent and refractory *Clostridium difficile* infection. *Aliment Pharm Therap* 2017;46:479-493. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apt.14201>.
- [62] Svensson CK, Cold F, Ribberholt I, et al. The Efficacy of Faecal Microbiota Transplant and Rectal Bacteriotherapy in Patients with Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection: A Retrospective Cohort Study. *Cells* 2022;11:3272. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11203272>.
- [63] Poylin V, Hawkins AT, Bhama AR, et al. The American Society of Colon and Rectal Surgeons Clinical Practice Guidelines for the Management of *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Dis Colon Rectum* 2021;64:650–68. <https://doi.org/10.1097/dcr.0000000000002047>.
- [64] Juul FE, Bretthauer M, Johnsen PH, et al. Fecal Microbiota Transplantation Versus Vancomycin for Primary *Clostridioides difficile* Infection: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Ann Intern Med* 2025. <https://doi.org/10.7326/annals-24-03285>.
- [65] Baunwall SMD, Andreasen SE, Hansen MM, et al. Faecal microbiota transplantation for first or second *Clostridioides difficile* infection (EarlyFMT): a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet Gastroenterology Hepatology* 2022. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-1253\(22\)00276-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-1253(22)00276-x).
- [66] Aby ES, Vaughn BP, Enns EA, et al. Cost-effectiveness of fecal microbiota transplantation for first recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* infection. *Clin Infect Dis* 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciac207>.
- [67] Marcella C, Cui B, Kelly CR, et al. Systematic review: the global incidence of faecal microbiota transplantation-related adverse events from 2000 to 2020. *Aliment Pharm Therap* 2021;53:33–42. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apt.16148>.
- [68] Yau YK, Lau LHS, Lui RNS, et al. Long-Term Safety Outcomes of Fecal Microbiota Transplantation: Real-World Data Over 8 Years From the Hong Kong FMT Registry. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2024;22:611-620.e12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cgh.2023.09.001>.
- [69] Perler BK, Chen B, Phelps E, et al. Long-Term Efficacy and Safety of Fecal Microbiota Transplantation for Treatment of Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *J Clin Gastroenterol* 2020;54:701–6. <https://doi.org/10.1097/mcg.0000000000001281>.
- [70] Saha S, Mara K, Pardi DS, et al. Long-term Safety of Fecal Microbiota Transplantation for Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Gastroenterology* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2021.01.010>.
- [71] Dawwas GK, Brensinger CM, Vajravelu RK, et al. Long-term Outcomes Following Multiply Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection and Fecal Microbiota Transplantation. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2022;20:806-816.e6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cgh.2020.12.004>.
- [72] Gupta S, Mullish BH, Allegretti JR. Fecal Microbiota Transplantation: The Evolving Risk Landscape. *Am J Gastroenterol* 2021;116:647–56. <https://doi.org/10.14309/ajg.0000000000001075>.

- [73] Berry P, Tariq R, Pardi D, et al. Effectiveness and Safety of Fecal Microbiota Transplantation for Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection in Immunocompromised Patients. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cgh.2025.06.043>.
- [74] Zhao Z, Wu Y, Geng X, et al. Efficacy of fidaxomicin versus vancomycin in the treatment of *Clostridium difficile* infection: A systematic meta-analysis. *Medicine* 2024;103:e39213. <https://doi.org/10.1097/md.00000000000039213>.
- [75] Gentry CA, Nguyen PK, Thind S, et al. Fidaxomicin versus oral vancomycin for severe *Clostridium difficile* infection: a retrospective cohort study. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2019;25:987–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2018.12.007>.
- [76] Cammarota G, Masucci L, Ianiro G, et al. Randomised clinical trial: faecal microbiota transplantation by colonoscopy vs. vancomycin for the treatment of recurrent *Clostridium difficile* infection. *Aliment Pharm Therap* 2015;41:835–43. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apt.13144>.
- [77] Tixier EN, Verheyen E, Luo Y, et al. Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis: Fecal Microbiota Transplantation for Severe or Fulminant *Clostridioides difficile*. *Dig Dis Sci* 2022;67:978–88. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10620-021-06908-4>.
- [78] Tixier EN, Verheyen E, Ungaro RC, et al. Faecal microbiota transplant decreases mortality in severe and fulminant *Clostridioides difficile* infection in critically ill patients. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2019;50:1094–9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apt.15526>.
- [79] Feuerstadt P, Louie TJ, Lashner B, et al. SER-109, an Oral Microbiome Therapy for Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *New Engl J Med* 2022;386:220–9. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2106516>.
- [80] Blair HA. SER-109 (VOWST™): A Review in the Prevention of Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Drugs* 2024;84:329–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40265-024-02006-7>.
- [81] Khanna S, Assi M, Lee C, et al. Efficacy and Safety of RBX2660 in PUNCH CD3, a Phase III, Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial with a Bayesian Primary Analysis for the Prevention of Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Drugs* 2022;82:1527–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40265-022-01797-x>.
- [82] Louie T, Golan Y, Khanna S, et al. VE303, a Defined Bacterial Consortium, for Prevention of Recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Jama* 2023;329:1356–66. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2023.4314>.
- [83] Tschudin-Sutter S, Kuijper EJ, Durovic A, et al. Guidance document for prevention of *Clostridium difficile* infection in acute healthcare settings. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2018;24:1051–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2018.02.020>.
- [84] Webb BJ, Subramanian A, Lopansri B, et al. Antibiotic Exposure and Risk for Hospital-Associated *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 2020;64:10.1128/aac.02169-19. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.02169-19>.

- [85] Liu Y, Dai M, Zhang K, et al. Risk of *Clostridioides difficile* infection following different antibiotics: insights from multi-source medical data. *Int J Antimicrob Agents* 2024;64:107288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijantimicag.2024.107288>.
- [86] Bella SD, Sanson G, Monticelli J, et al. *Clostridioides difficile* infection: history, epidemiology, risk factors, prevention, clinical manifestations, treatment, and future options. *Clin Microbiol Rev* 2024;37:e00135-23. <https://doi.org/10.1128/cmr.00135-23>.
- [87] Ray MJ, Strnad LC, Tucker KJ, et al. Influence of Antibiotic Exposure Intensity on the Risk of *Clostridioides difficile* Infection. *Clin Infect Dis* 2024;79:1129–35. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciae259>.
- [88] Brown KA, Khanafer N, Daneman N, et al. Meta-Analysis of Antibiotics and the Risk of Community-Associated *Clostridium difficile* Infection. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 2013;57:2326–32. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.02176-12>.
- [89] Azab M, Doo L, Doo DH, et al. Comparison of the Hospital-Acquired *Clostridium difficile* Infection Risk of Using Proton Pump Inhibitors versus Histamine-2 Receptor Antagonists for Prophylaxis and Treatment of Stress Ulcers: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Gut Liver* 2017;11:781–8. <https://doi.org/10.5009/gnl16568>.
- [90] Eeuwijk J, Ferreira G, Yarzabal JP, et al. A Systematic Literature Review on Risk Factors for and Timing of *Clostridioides difficile* Infection in the United States. *Infect Dis Ther* 2024;13:273–98. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40121-024-00919-0>.
- [91] Finke M, Boven A, Vlieghe E, et al. Proton pump inhibitors and the risk of *Clostridioides difficile* infection: A systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis. *J Infect* 2025;90:106488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2025.106488>.
- [92] Floria D-E, Obeidat M, Vánca S, et al. Proton pump inhibitors are not associated with an increased risk of *Clostridioides difficile* infection: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Gut Microbes* 2025;17:2562341. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19490976.2025.2562341>.
- [93] Moayyedi P, Eikelboom JW, Bosch J, et al. Safety of Proton Pump Inhibitors Based on a Large, Multi-Year, Randomized Trial of Patients Receiving Rivaroxaban or Aspirin. *Gastroenterology* 2019;157:682-691.e2. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2019.05.056>.
- [94] Anjewierden S, Han Z, Brown AM, et al. Risk factors for *Clostridioides difficile* colonization among hospitalized adults: A meta-analysis and systematic review. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiology* 2020;42:565–72. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ice.2020.1236>.
- [95] Cannon CM, Musuuza JS, Barker AK, et al. Risk of *Clostridium difficile* Infection in Hematology-Oncology Patients Colonized With Toxigenic *C. difficile*. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiology* 2017;38:718–20. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ice.2017.48>.
- [96] Ford CD, Lopansri BK, Webb BJ, et al. *Clostridioides difficile* colonization and infection in patients with newly diagnosed acute leukemia: Incidence, risk factors, and patient outcomes. *Am J Infect Control* 2019;47:394–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2018.09.027>.

- [97] Fuereder T, Koni D, Gleiss A, et al. Risk factors for Clostridium difficile infection in hemato-oncological patients: A case control study in 144 patients. Sci Rep 2016;6:31498. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep31498>.
- [98] Milenković B, Šuljagić V, Perić A, et al. Outcomes of Clostridioides difficile infection in adult cancer and non-cancer patients hospitalised in a tertiary hospital: a prospective cohort study. Eur J Hosp Pharm 2022;29:e15–22. <https://doi.org/10.1136/ejhpharm-2020-002574>.
- [99] Larrainzar-Coghen T, Rodriguez-Pardo D, Barba P, et al. Prognosis of Clostridium difficile infection in adult oncohaematological patients: experience from a large prospective observational study. Eur J Clin Microbiol 2018;37:2075–82. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10096-018-3341-4>.
- [100] De-la-Rosa-Martinez D, Zinser-Peniche P, Martin-Onraet A, et al. Performance of Clostridioides difficile infection severity scores and risk factors related to 30-day all-cause mortality in patients with cancer. Support Care Cancer 2023;31:187. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-023-07651-4>.
- [101] Hung Y-P, Tsai C-S, Tsai B-Y, et al. Clostridioides difficile infection in patients with hematological malignancy: A multicenter study in Taiwan. J Microbiol, Immunol Infect 2021;54:1101–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmii.2021.02.002>.

Non severe CDI

Clinical features

Clinical symptoms compatible with CDI

OR

Pseudomembranous colitis diagnosed after endoscopy, colectomy, or autopsy

+

Microbiological evidence

Multistep diagnosis using

GDH antigen assay

Toxin A/B enzyme immunoassay

Nucleic acid amplification test

+

No alternate diagnosis

Severe CDI

Severe

One of the following criteria

- Leukocytosis $\geq 15\ 000$ cells/mL
- Serum creatinine level >1.5 mg/dL or rise in serum creatinine $>50\%$ of baseline
- Core body temperature $>38^{\circ}5C$

Complicated CDI

Complicated

- Hypotension
- Septic shock
- Elevated serum lactate
- Ileus
- Toxic megacolon
- Bowel perforation
- Any fulminant course of disease

Product

FMT

FMT-derived
RBX 2660

SER 109

Bacterial consortia
VE 303

Patients

Fresh, frozen,
capsules, enema

Liquid enema

Oral capsules

Oral capsules

Median nb
of recc: 3

≥ 1 recc ou ≥ 2
severe in the
past year

≥ 3 CDI
within 12
months

>1 CDI within 6 months
or high risk for
recurrence (age, renal
insuf, ppi, CDI history)

rCDI Risk
Reduction

64%

13.1%

28%

31.7%

van Nood et al, N Engl J
Med 2013;368:407-15.

Khanna et al, Drugs
(2022) 82:1527-1538

Feuerstadt et al, N Engl
J Med 2022;386:220-9.

Louie et al, JAMA.
2023;329(16):1356-1366

2026 Swiss society of Infectious diseases recommendations for *Clostridioides difficile* Infection (CDI)

Supplementary Material

Table S1. Workflow of the guideline development Pages 2- 4

Table S2. Composition of the working groups (WG) Page 5

Table S1. Workflow of the guideline development

Task	Who	What
Design / conceptualization; level: leading committee		
Definition of working groups (WG) and group leaders	SSI executive committee	Definition of 4 WG: definitions, risk factors, treatment and hygiene/prevention.
Constitution of the WGs	Group leaders	Designation of 4 group leaders among the scientific committee according to their expertise in the field.
Determination of questions to answer	Group leaders	For each WG, a subset of practical questions to answer (i.e. relevant for clinical practice) were defined.
Analysis / Interpretation; level: each working group (WG)		
Literature review	Group leaders and senior reviewers	Selection of relevant articles (literature search) for each topic and questions to answer.
Compilation of evidences	Group leaders and senior reviewers	Analyses of selected articles. Constitution of a core of evidence-based elements to answer the questions.
Proposition of recommendation	All WG members (group leaders, senior reviewers)	Review of the core of evidence-based elements and proposition of recommendation based on these elements.
Discussion for recommendations; level: all participants		
Presentation of results and preliminary recommendations	Plenary webex: all participants (group leaders, senior reviewers) All participants were required	Presentation of the results by each WG.

Analysis of the recommendations	All participants (group leaders, senior reviewers)	Results and recommendations were analyzed by all the participants. All the comments were then gathered to be discussed in the last plenary Webex. The participants were invited to send by email their potential comments or disagreements.
Plenary session final discussion	Plenary Webex: all participants (group leaders, senior reviewers) All participants were required	All comments were discussed to reach a consensus.
Preparation of manuscript; level: all participants		
First draft of individual chapters	Each group leader	Each WG, redaction of their dedicated chapter after discussion of the evidence in the WG
First draft of the complete manuscript	B Guery	Introduction and methodology, merging of all different chapters, harmonization of style and length, finalization of tables / figures.
Review / editing of manuscript	All participants	Manuscript was sent by email to all participants for review. Approval of all participants was required for co-authorship.
Finalization of the manuscript	B Guery	Implementation of edits of the participants. Implementation following the changes suggested in the final plenary Webex.

Table S2. Composition of the working groups (WG)

Last name, first name	Specialty	Role
WG 1: definitions		
Prendki, Virginie	Geriatrics, Infectious diseases	Group leader
Guery, Benoit	Infectious diseases	Senior reviewer
WG 2: risk factors		
Brugger, Silvio D	Infectious diseases	Group leader
Prendki, Virginie	Geriatrics, Infectious diseases	Senior reviewer
Martischang, Romain	Infectious diseases	Senior reviewer
WG 3: treatment		
Guery, Benoit	Infectious diseases	Group leader
Albrich, Werner	Infectious diseases	Senior reviewer
Brugger, Silvio D	Infectious diseases	Group leader
WG 4: hygiene and prevention		
Tschudin-Sutter, Sarah	Hygiene, Infectious diseases	Group leader
Stroffolini, Giacomo	Hygiene, Infectious diseases	Senior reviewer